

Highlights

Can a boost in oil prices suspend the evolution of the green transportation market? Factors driving the dynamic conditional correlation between green indices and Brent oil prices

Agata Kliber,Blanka Łęć,Pavel Rezac

- We investigate relationships between oil and green indices related to alternative fuels and transport modes.
- We estimate dynamic correlations between Brent and each index and explain their changes with fundamental and speculation-related factors.
- Speculation does not affect the relationships between Brent and green indices.
- The effect of increasing oil prices on indices' prices can be twofold - depending on the origin of the change.

Can a boost in oil prices suspend the evolution of the green transportation market? Factors driving the dynamic conditional correlation between green indices and Brent oil prices

Agata Kliber^{a,*}, Blanka Łęt^a and Pavel Rezac^b

^aPoznan University of Economics and Business, Al. Niepodleglosci 10, Poznan, 60-867, Poland

^bTransport Research Centre, CDV, Líšeňská 33a, Brno, 636 00, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Brent oil
alternative fuels
green transport
investment
financialization
speculation

ABSTRACT

The research aims to answer whether the increases in oil prices can hinder the development of the alternative fuels market and green transportation modes. On the one hand, the growing oil prices encourage individuals to choose alternative transport modes. Conversely, the boosts in oil prices attract investors to the oil market instead of alternative fuels. We analyse the relationships between oil and green indices related to widely-understood transport during 2018-2022. We investigate factors that affect these relationships, distinguishing between fundamentals and speculation. We discover that fundamental factors are predominant in shaping the correlation between Brent and green indices. In two of the three analysed cases, the correlation was positive during the studied period, which means that the indices grew together with Brent prices. We show that the effect of increasing oil prices can be twofold - depending on the origin of the change. It can contribute to the interest in alternative transport growth if it results from oil demand shocks driven by economic activity. However, a boost in oil prices following positive oil consumption demand shocks or expectations about future oil price increases can cause capital outflow from the alternative transportation market.

1. Introduction

Transport accounts for around one-fifth of global CO_2 emissions, from which three-quarters come from road transport [50]. The International Energy Agency (IEA) expects that by 2070 global transport (in passenger-kilometers) will double, car ownership rates will increase by 60%, and demand for passenger and freight aviation will triple [33]. One of the solutions to limit the excessive emission of carbon dioxide is to switch to so-called green transport gradually. The latter concept encompasses all those transportation means that affect the human health and environment less than the existing transportation services [9]. By green transport, one understands electric vehicles and the technology that utilizes biogas or other biofuels [39, 52].

The development of the green transport sector and the adaptation of a low-emission economy are influenced by regulations at the national and international levels. In the European Union, according to a European Parliament regulation, all new passenger cars and vans sold in the EU from 2035 should produce no CO_2 emissions. That should ensure that the transport sector becomes carbon neutral by 2050. In the United States, the Renewable Fuel Standard Program mandates that transportation fuel sold in the country should contain a minimum volume of renewable fuels, increasing yearly.¹

The necessity of looking for an alternative to fossil fuels source of energy becomes apparent each time when an oil-related crisis breaks out. That is especially true in the case of the transportation sector, where energy-efficient cars are preferred when oil price shocks occur (see e.g. [35]). The COVID-19 pandemic, followed by mobility restrictions, the Russian invasion of Ukraine, and the ban on the import of fuels from Russia, affect to a great degree the prices of fuels, especially oil. Since the drastic decline at the beginning of the pandemic, oil prices have been steadily growing. The growth intensified together with the outbreak of the war in Ukraine.

There are at least two competing theories explaining the dynamics of oil (as one of the commodities) prices. According to the supply and demand theory, commodities prices are shaped by supply and demand forces, including

*Corresponding author

✉ agata.kliber@ue.poznan.pl (A. Kliber); blanka.let@ue.poznan.pl (B. Łęt); pavel.rezac@cdv.cz (P. Rezac)
ORCID(s): 0000-0001-7511-2910 (A. Kliber); 0000-0001-5107-1456 (B. Łęt); 0000-0003-1585-1409 (P. Rezac)

¹<https://www.epa.gov/renewable-fuel-standard-program>

the level of production, consumption patterns, geopolitical instability, weather conditions and government policies. Another theory is the financial speculation one, suggesting that commodity prices are predominantly determined by speculative activities in financial markets, reflecting the trading behavior of hedge funds, institutional investors, and commodity index funds. Numerous empirical studies have attempted to disentangle the effects of these two factors - see e.g. [13, 20, 56]. However, previous studies have not considered how such factors affect the interplay between oil prices and the green transport sector.

In our paper, we analyse the interrelationships between oil prices and selected green transport-related indices comprising companies from all over the world and verify whether the changes in the relationships resulted from fundamental factors driving oil dynamics, geopolitical factors or financial ones (thus - resulting from possible speculation). We estimate the volatilities of oil prices and green indices, as well as the dynamic correlation between each pair of assets: Brent-green index. Next, we verify whether the dynamic correlation between them reacts to the changes in fundamental factors (such as demand and supply shocks, global industrial production, global economic activity and commodity prices), the overall situation in financial markets (proxied by S&P 500) or the changes in expectations regarding Brent oil prices (expectations derived by the US Energy Information Association and indices directly related to speculation). The article aims to verify the thesis that increasing oil prices can contribute to the outflow of capital from the alternative fuels market. The issue is of particular importance as the costs of renewable energy technologies are susceptible to financing terms [55].

We analyze the relationships between the crude Brent prices and the green indices comprising companies from all over the world: NASDAQ OMX Bio/Clean Fuels Index (GRNBIO), NASDAQ OMX Fuel Cell Index (GRNFUEL) and NASDAQ OMX Transportation Index (GRNTRN). We first estimate univariate GARCH models for each series. Next, we calculate dynamic conditional correlations based on these estimates. Finally, we regress the monthly averages of the dynamic correlations on the fundamental and speculative factors to disentangle which - if any - contributed to the weakening of the relationships between Brent and green indices. Weakening of correlation during Brent increases signifies the investors' decreasing interest in alternative fuels or transport modes.

We show that the correlation between Brent and the indices was usually positive, which means that the increase in oil prices co-occurred with the rise in interest in alternative fuels and transport modes. That can suggest that the investors anticipate the shift in interest of the consumers' demand. Yet, we observed episodes of negative correlation in the case of the pair Brent-GRNTRN (the index that tracks companies focused on efficiency gains and pollution reduction). The largest drops appeared at the beginning of the COVID period. The downfalls in correlation were caused by positive oil demand shocks and the deterioration of global economic conditions. Expectations about future growth in Brent prices contributed to a decline in correlation between Brent and companies producing energy from fuel cells. Purely speculative factors did not affect significantly the correlation between Brent and the indices.

Our paper contributes to the literature in the following ways. Firstly, contrary to most of the research that investigates the influence of fundamental and speculative factors on oil volatility, we concentrate on their impact on the changes in the dynamic correlation between Brent and alternative transportation indices. Secondly, we focus specifically on transportation-related indices, as the transportation sector was severely affected by the movement restrictions imposed during COVID-19 and, later, influenced by the increasing oil prices. Thirdly, our conclusions are general since we analyze the relationship between Brent crude oil, considered the global benchmark for the oil price, and green indices constructed based on data about the world's largest companies dealing with green transport and fuels alternative to oil. Eventually, we distinguish between the nature of the factors that shape these correlations depending on the type of indices studied.

The rest of the article is organised as follows. Section 2 gives in-depth review of the existing literature. Section 3 describes the data used, including data on fundamental and speculative factors. Section 4 describes the methodology used to estimate the conditional correlations between two markets. Section 5 gives main empirical results and Section 6 concludes.

2. Literature review

Highly volatile oil prices, geopolitical instability of countries that control most of the oil reserves, rising demand for passenger transportation, and environmental issues (such as climate change) are the main drivers for the increased usage of biofuels [45]. In this paper, we concentrate on the first incentive, i. e., the instability of oil prices as a potential driver or an obstacle to the transformation to green transportation. We study the problem from the point of view of potential investors who locate their wealth in fuel-related companies.

With the development of the green energy markets, the number of opportunities to invest in green companies has been steadily growing. The alternatives rise from alternative energy mutual funds, through exchange-traded funds (ETFs), to passive replication of market indices. The performance of such investment attracts the attention of both scholars and practitioners.

One strand of the literature analyzes the effectiveness of investing in the green energy sector. Some authors compare it with the performance of firms from other economic sectors. For instance, [48] studied the financial performance of alternative energy mutual funds over the period 2010–2016. The authors found that alternative energy funds underperformed corporate and socially responsible mutual funds regarding returns and downside risk protection. The scholars concluded that investors paid a premium for going green via renewable energies. [42], who analyzed a sample of 4496 mutual funds commercialized in Europe from 2007 to 2018, has reached a similar conclusion. These funds underperformed their conventional peers but performed similarly to black energy funds.

Regarding indices, [49] documented that the renewable energy indices' risk-adjusted return was unexceptionally low and that renewables were not a financially attractive portfolio investment from 2000 to 2013. [28], who analyzed Dow Jones Sustainability Indexes (DJSI) and several renewable energy indexes from December 31, 2010, to December 31, 2019, formulated similar conclusions. During that period, renewable energy indexes had high betas and negative returns and thus were unattractive to investors. [38] also showed that between October 2010 and May 2021, clean energy stocks generally underperformed the overall equity market measured by the NASDAQ index.

Other authors compared the effectiveness of investment in the green energy sector with the traditional energy sector. [43] evaluated the performance of Alternative Energy and Energy ETFs comparing five energy ETFs and five alternative energy ETFs from 2007 to 2018. ETFs are passive investments that are traded like shares and mirror the performance of a sector or a market index. The authors showed that Alternative Energy ETFs outperformed Energy ETFs and maintained this better performance for many out-of-samples, including those whose in-sample periods coincided with high oil and gas prices. However, [1] reached the opposite conclusion, analyzing analogous ETFs in three subperiods: the period 2006–2013 with the financial crisis included, the period 2014–2016 with the great fall of oil prices included, and their junction including both shocks.

Regarding stocks, [16] compared portfolios of green energy European stocks and their non-green counterparts from January 2008 to November 2020. The authors concluded that the investment in green energy firms performed at least as well as in their non-green counterparts. Similarly, [38] proved that “clean energy” stocks generally outperformed dirty stocks in terms of risk-adjusted returns.

Yet another scholars concentrated on the interrelationships between the oil and green energy sectors. For instance, [47] analyzed the systemic risk between oil and renewable energy stock prices from December 2005 to December 2013. Their results indicate a time-varying positive average dependence and symmetrical tail dependence for all the indices except for the solar energy index, where tail dependence was asymmetrical. The main conclusion from the research was that policy-oriented strategies aimed at facilitating the transition to a sustainable energy system ought to be implemented asymmetrically — reinforced when oil prices are low and relaxed when oil prices are high. [51] formulated similar conclusions, analysing relationships between renewable energy investment, oil prices, GDP and the interest rate in three countries with different relationships with the renewable energy sector: Norway and the UK being oil exporters for most of the sample and the USA - an importer. In a more recent study, [61] used the copula framework to investigate the relationship between the oil and clean energy sub-sectors and revealed that the tail dependence index in the right tail was firmer in the pre-COVID period. On the contrary, in the COVID-19 period, the left-tail dependence was stronger.

In another work related to ours, [2] analyzed the dependence between oil and clean energy assets using VAR for the VaR framework in the pre-COVID period (until May 2019). The authors run the [12] test as well. Specifically, they compared the causality in tails in the pre-and post-Paris agreement periods (September 2011 - December 2015 and December 2015 - May 2019). Their results revealed a symmetrical spillover effect between the clean energy sector and oil returns. The causality effect of oil on the downside risk of green energy assets' returns occurred before the Paris Agreement. Conversely, extremely high oil returns preceded a similar trend in the clean energy sector only after the Paris Agreement. Analogous conclusions were formulated by [29].

[14] documented strong cross-sector herding spillovers and risk spillovers from the US fossil fuels market to any renewable energy markets. The authors proved that investors are more likely to display herding behaviour during extremely low oil price returns, particularly in the fossil fuel energy sectors. Similarly, [54], who used VAR for the VaR method in the period 2010-2020, found, inter alia, that biofuel-related companies and fuel cells sub-sector are affected by the oil price declines mainly in the left tail of the distribution. Comparable conclusions were reached by [53], who

examined the relationship between oil prices and the indices of renewable energy and technology companies using Quantile Regression, Quantile-on-Quantile Regression, and Granger-Causality in Quantiles. The authors document asymmetric relationships between the sectors, which were stronger when these variables decreased than increased, which confirms the conclusions by [17].

[46], using a connectedness framework and dynamic conditional correlation models, proved that the interdependence of the biofuel sub-sector with oil returns was stronger than fuel cell stocks. The period covered in the study was from October 2010 to August 2018. Similarly, [32] analysed the relationship between oil shocks and green equities using wavelet coherence and frequency connectedness techniques. The authors concluded, *inter alia*, that the relationships between the sectors are more pronounced in the medium- and long-term. Contrarywise, [26], who used the Tail-Event driven NETWORKS risk model, showed that the clean energy market and the oil market are generally quite separated, as each sector receives risk mainly from itself.

Regarding transport-related research, we should note the work of [8], who analysed the sensitivity of the world's largest automobile manufacturers to oil price changes. The authors concluded that increasing oil prices may shift demand towards more environmentally friendly vehicles and vice versa. They suggested that there was a substitution effect between traditional cars and electric cars partially driven by the price of oil (see also [15]). Also [60] documented significant relationships between the global crude oil market and the European markets of biodiesel and rapeseed oil and shifts in the dynamics of quantile dependency during periods of financial and economic turmoil.

A prevailing body of research concentrates simply on the existence of the relationships between oil and renewable energy markets or the direction of causality. We found no paper explaining the sources of the relationship changes. Some researchers focused on the nature of the correlation between oil and the broad stock market. Such one is [24], who explained the changes in correlation between oil prices and financial markets in oil-importing and oil-exporting countries considering the origin of oil price shocks. The authors considered aggregate demand-side shock, precautionary demand shock and supply-side shock. Also [40] concentrated on the sources of interrelationships between oil and the stock market and explained them with economic policy uncertainty. In a very recent paper, [25] demonstrated that the covariance between oil, gold, and the stock market is driven by attention measured with Google searches. Nevertheless, no paper concentrates directly on the sources of the interrelationship between the oil and indices related to alternative transport market. Our paper aims to fill this gap.

3. Data

3.1. Brent and green indices

We analyze data on oil Brent futures prices together with global green indices related to the transportation market, i.e.

- NASDAQ OMX Bio/Clean Fuels Index (GRNBIO) - a primary sector index of the Green Economy Index, designed to track companies listed on various stock exchanges around the world that manufacture fuels from a plant-based material that replaces petroleum-based fuels for transportation.²
- NASDAQ OMX Fuel Cell Index (GRNFUEL) - a sub-sector index of the Green Economy Index designed to track companies listed on various stock exchanges around the world that produce energy through fuel cells. The Fuel Cell Index rolls up to the primary sector Renewable Energy Generation Index.³
- NASDAQ OMX Transportation Index (GRNTRN) - a primary sector index of the Green Economy Index designed to track companies listed on various stock exchanges around the world focused on efficiency gains and pollution reduction associated with automobiles, trains, and other modes of transportation.⁴ //

The research period covers January 2018-December 2022. The source of oil data is the nasdaq.com database (BZ:NMX). We obtained the NASDAQ indices through the Nasdaqomx website. We note that the indices encompass companies from all over the world.

In Figure 1, we present the logarithms of oil prices and indices' prices. We observe a steep increase in the value of most indices connected with green transport just after the sharp declines at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. The growth was especially spectacular in the case of GRNTRN.

²<https://indexes.nasdaqomx.com/Index/Overview/GRNBIO>

³<https://indexes.nasdaqomx.com/Index/Overview/GRNFUEL>

⁴<https://indexes.nasdaqomx.com/Index/Overview/GRNTRN>

Figure 1: Logarithmic prices of Brent oil versus green indices

Table 1
Data characteristics

	Brent	GRNBIO	GRNFUEL	GRNTRN
Mean	0.000	-0.000	0.001	0.001
Median	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001
Std.deviation	0.030	0.024	0.040	0.024
Min	-0.280	-0.182	-0.208	-0.137
Max	0.274	0.134	0.216	0.114
Kurtosis	21.321	9.081	3.208	4.227
Skewness	-0.886	-1.074	0.202	-0.376

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics. We observe the exceptional value of the kurtosis of Brent returns (21.32). Such a high value of this statistic indicates the presence of outliers in the data. Indeed, the COVID-19 period, with its mobility restrictions, caused drastic day-by-day changes in oil prices.

3.2. Fundamentals driving oil prices volatility

The literature explains the volatility of oil with supply and demand factors, geopolitical events, government policies, expectations and speculation (see, e.g. [13, 20, 56, 7, 5, 4, 35, 34]). Based on these theories, we expect that a similar group of factors may shape the correlation between Brent and alternative fuels. We analyse monthly data on oil supply and demand shocks, commodities prices, global economic policy instability, and world industrial production to account for fundamental factors. They are proxied by the following magnitudes:

- D.WIP: changes in world industrial production index collected from [5], a monthly index of industrial production covering OECD countries and six major emerging markets; due to the nonstationarity of the data, included as log-differences in the model;
- COMM: real commodity price factor - obtained from [4], a common factor extracted from a panel of real commodity prices;
- D.GECON: changes in global economic condition indicator (standardised) - obtained from [6]: first principal component from the panel of 16 variables related to real economic activity, commodity prices, financial indicators, transportation, uncertainty, expectations, weather, and energy-related measures; included as differences in the model;
- S.SH: oil supply shock - obtained from [5]; due to the nonstationarity of the data, included as log-differences in the model;
- three oil demand shocks: OCDSH: oil consumption demand, OIDSH: oil inventory demand, and EASH: oil demand shocks driven by global economic activity [5];
- D.GEPU: changes in global economic policy uncertainty index - obtained from [3], a normalised index of the volume of news articles discussing economic policy uncertainty; due to the nonstationarity of the data, included as log-differences in the model;
- D.EXP: changes in Brent spot prices expectations formulated by the U.S. Energy Information Association; due to the non-stationarity of the index, we included it as log-differences into the model;

In Figure 2, we present the dynamics of the indices. We note the deep shock of oil consumption demand at the beginning of COVID pandemic, followed by the shock of global economic conditions.

3.3. Speculation-related factors driving oil prices volatility

There is no unique definition of speculation in the oil market [23, 11]. For instance, [36] defined speculation as buying crude not for current consumption but for future use, including buying oil for physical storage, which leads to the accumulation of inventories. As noted by [23], such speculation does not have to be morally reprehensible, opposite to the so-called "excessive speculation". Nevertheless, it is difficult to determine whether speculation is excessive. One possible approach is to determine who engages in speculation. However, the presence of speculation by so-called non-commercial traders also does not reveal whether the speculation is excessive. Thus, Working [59] defined speculation as the percentage of speculation over what is minimally needed to meet short and long-hedging demand.

Following the discussion, we collected two factors that can be related to the speculation. These are:

- L.SPC: Net position of Money Managers (long-short) for Brent contract - based on the ICE Futures Europe Commitments of Traders Reports (www.ice.com/marketdata/reports/122). The category "Managed Money" reflects positions of entities managing futures trading on behalf of clients and investment firms⁵. A positive index value denotes an excess of long over short positions and is interpreted as an optimistic investors' sentiment related to the oil market. The data proved to be stationary, according to the ADF test. Yet, due to its magnitude, we included in the model its log-values;
- D.SPC: Speculation measure analogous to Working's [59] index, which measures the speculative activity of non-commercial traders in the crude oil market ("Managed Money" and "Other Reportables"⁶), relative to hedging activity of commercial traders - entities with exposure to the underlying physical market for crude oil ("Producer/Merchant/Processor/User" category in the COT Reports). The index is calculated as:

$$T_{mod} = \begin{cases} 1 + \frac{NCS}{HS+HL}, & \text{if } HS \geq HL \\ 1 + \frac{NCL}{HS+HL}, & \text{if } HS < HL, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

⁵Examples include hedge funds, pension funds, registered US commodity trading advisors or commodity pool operators.

⁶Examples include proprietary (multi-asset) trading houses, algorithmic traders and local traders.

Figure 2: Supply and demand shocks, policy uncertainty(log-differences), global economic conditions (differences), commodity prices, expectations and industrial production (log differences)

where NCS is non-commercial short positions, NCL is non-commercial long positions, HS is short hedge positions, and HL is long hedge positions ⁷. Due to the nonstationarity of the data, we included it in the model as log-differences;

- S.SPX: Log-returns of S&P 500 index, a control measure for the overall conditions in financial markets. Due to the non-stationarity of the data, we included it as log-differences in the model.

In Figure 3, we present the dynamics of log-differences of S&P, log-position of money managers (L.SPC) and log-differences of modified Working index (D.SPC) [59]. We observe the increase in speculation (D.SPC) at the beginning of COVID period, after the unexpected drop in oil prices.

In Table 2, we present correlation matrix of the fundamental and speculative over the whole analysed period. We observe a high correlation between world industrial production (WIP) and economic activity shock (0.94) and global economic conditions (0.65). Expectations are highly positively correlated with oil consumption demand shocks (0.79) and negatively - with supply shocks (-0.71). We also note that S&P index is only moderately correlated with oil supply and demand shocks, nor with the expectations regarding future oil prices, which corroborated the results obtained by [37].

⁷We excluded the positions of "Swap Dealer" from the commercial traders category, due to the concerns related to their speculative activity in the oil market. Traditionally (before September 2009), COT Reports classified swap dealers as commercials. However, their trading activity may be considered speculative [18].

Figure 3: Financial factors affecting oil prices: log-differences of S&P, log-position of money managers (L.SPC) and log-differences of modified Working index (D.SPC)

4. Methods

All the methods used in the study rely on volatility estimates of the indices. Thus, in the first step of the research, we estimate univariate GARCH models for Brent oil prices and each of the indexes separately. Next, we use standardized residuals to obtain dynamic conditional correlation. The models were estimated in R using packages rugarch [30] and rmgarch [27]. Eventually, we regress the conditional correlations against the set of fundamental and speculative factors. In this way, we test whether changes in correlations were caused by fundamentals driving oil volatility or by speculative factors. Suppose the relationship between the factors and correlation is negative. In that case, we conclude that the increase in oil prices is followed by the decrease in the alternative fuels price and thus - the capital may flow from the alternative fuels to the oil market.

4.1. Volatility models

Let us denote by y_t a vector of the log-returns of the financial instrument (here: Brent price or green transport indices) and by Ω_{t-1} - the set of information available up to the moment $(t - 1)$. Let us denote the conditional mean of

Table 2
Correlation of fundamentals and speculative factors

	D.WIP	COM	D.GECON	S.SH	EASH	OCDSH	OIDSH	D.GEPU	D.EXP	L.SPC	D.SPC	D.SPX
D.WIP	1.00	0.21	0.65	-0.28	0.94	0.19	-0.21	-0.07	0.55	-0.02	0.13	-0.11
COM	0.21	1.00	0.31	-0.22	0.09	0.28	0.21	-0.22	0.40	0.07	0.12	0.21
D.GECON	0.65	0.31	1.00	-0.32	0.60	0.31	-0.07	-0.33	0.57	0.21	0.03	0.15
S.SH	-0.28	-0.22	-0.32	1.00	-0.36	-0.51	0.08	0.13	-0.71	-0.07	0.16	-0.20
EASH	0.94	0.09	0.60	-0.36	1.00	0.21	-0.23	-0.05	0.52	-0.03	0.14	-0.12
OCDSH	0.19	0.28	0.31	-0.51	0.21	1.00	-0.36	-0.28	0.79	0.42	-0.29	0.35
OIDSH	-0.21	0.21	-0.07	0.08	-0.23	-0.36	1.00	-0.04	-0.14	0.10	-0.01	-0.03
D.GEPU	-0.07	-0.22	-0.33	0.13	-0.05	-0.28	-0.04	1.00	-0.21	-0.23	0.10	-0.02
D.EXP	0.55	0.40	0.57	-0.71	0.52	0.79	-0.14	-0.21	1.00	0.36	-0.16	0.27
L.SPC	-0.02	0.07	0.21	-0.07	-0.03	0.42	0.10	-0.23	0.36	1.00	-0.43	0.13
D.SPC	0.13	0.12	0.03	0.16	0.14	-0.29	-0.01	0.10	-0.16	-0.43	1.00	-0.22
D.SPX	-0.11	0.21	0.15	-0.20	-0.12	0.35	-0.03	-0.02	0.27	0.13	-0.22	1.00

y_t as:

$$y_t = E(y_t | \Omega_{t-1}) + \epsilon_t, \quad (2)$$

where $E(\cdot | \cdot)$ denotes the conditional expectation operator, while ϵ_t is the disturbance term with $E(\epsilon_t) = 0$ and for all $t \neq s$: $E(\epsilon_t, \epsilon_s) = 0$.

One of the most widely used specifications of the conditional mean are the ARMA-type models. In the case of most financial time-series data, the ϵ_t can be decomposed in the following way:

$$\epsilon_t = z_t \sigma_t, \quad (3)$$

where $z_t \sim iid$ with mean 0 and unit variance. If σ_t can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_i \epsilon_{t-i}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j \sigma_{t-j}^2, \quad (4)$$

we say that it follows a GARCH(p, q) process (see: [10] for details).

Since the pioneering work of [10], many other specifications have appeared. First of all, different distribution of errors has been allowed (e.g., Student, skewed Student, or generalized error distribution: GED). From various functional specifications of GARCH models, we used a GJR model of [31]. A GJR model takes the following form:

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \sum_{i=1}^q (\alpha_j y_{t-i}^2 + \gamma_j I_{(y_{t-i} < 0)}) y_{t-i}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j \sigma_{t-j}^2, \quad (5)$$

where $I_{(\cdot)}$ is an indicator function (i.e. $I_{(y_{t-1} < 0)} = 1$) if $y_{t-1} < 0$ and 0 otherwise, and γ denotes the asymmetry parameter.

4.2. Dynamic conditional correlation

To model the conditional correlation between Brent and green indices, we used the bivariate DCC-GARCH model [21]. Let us denote by $\epsilon_t = (\epsilon_{1,t}, \epsilon_{2,t})'$ a two-dimensional vector. The DCC model assumes:

$$\epsilon_t | \Omega_{t-1} \sim N(0, H_t), H_t = D_t R_t D_t, \quad (6)$$

where $D_t = \text{diag}(\sqrt{h_{11,t}}, \sqrt{h_{22,t}})$ and conditional variance $h_{ii,t}$ is modelled using the GARCH-type models. In turn, the conditional correlation matrix R_t is given by

$$R_t = (\text{diag}(Q_t))^{-1/2} Q_t (\text{diag}(Q_t))^{-1/2}, \quad (7)$$

Can a boost in oil prices suspend the evolution of the green transportation market?

with

$$Q_t = (1 - a - b)Q^* + az_{t-1}z'_{t-1} + bQ_{t-1}, \quad (8)$$

where Q^* is unconditional covariance matrix of z_t ($z_{i,t} = \epsilon_{i,t}/\sqrt{h_{ii,t}}$); a, b are parameters such that $a, b \geq 0$ and $a + b < 1$.

As an alternative, we also tested for the adequacy of asymmetric DCC model. The symmetric DCC was superior in each case.

5. Results

The results are presented in the following order. First, we show the estimates of ARMA-GARCH models, next, we describe the dynamic conditional correlation estimates. Eventually, we investigate factors that contribute to the lowering in correlations between Brent and alternative fuels - either fundamental or speculative ones.

5.1. Volatility estimates

In the first step of the research, we estimated univariate volatility models for Brent and each index for the whole period of the study. Each time, the best ARMA-GARCH model was chosen based on the following criteria:

- ability to explain all linear and non-linear dependencies in the data (Box-Pierce, Ljung-Box and ARCH tests on residuals and squared residuals);
- significance of the parameters α , β and ω . If we were unable to obtain significant ω , we used the variance-targeting option;
- stationarity condition, i.e. $\alpha + \beta < 1$ for GARCH (1,1) model and $\alpha + \beta + 0.5 \cdot \gamma < 1$ for GJR;
- goodness of fit of the distribution (Pearson's test);
- stability of the parameters (Nyblom's test);
- ability to explain the possible asymmetry in the volatility (sign-bias test).

There were two cases when some of the criteria were not met. The best model that explained the volatility of Brent did not pass the sign-bias test. According to the test, there was no positive nor negative bias in the residuals, yet - we could not explain the total asymmetry in the residuals (the joint effect was still present) - see Table 3 for details. The second such model was the volatility model for GRNBIO, where we could not fit the proper distribution to residuals.

In sum, the best models were:

- GJR-GARCH with skewed Student distribution for Brent (Tab. 3)
- GARCH(1,1) with Student distribution for GRNFUEL (Tab. 4) and GRNTRN (Tab.4);
- GARCH(1,1) with skewed Student distribution for GRNBIO (Tab.5).

In Fig. 4, we present the time-varying volatilities of analyzed instruments. The volatility of Brent is painted in a black dotted line, while the volatility of each green index is in green. Undoubtedly, all of them experienced the highest volatility growth during the COVID period. The increase in volatility of Brent at the beginning of the Russo-Ukrainian war was the second-highest peak, and it did not have a counterpart in the volatilities of green-fuel indices.

5.2. Influence of oil supply and demand shocks on correlation between oil and green indices

Based on volatility models estimated in the previous section, we estimate bivariate DCC models. We obtain daily estimates of the conditional correlation between Brent and each asset in each case. The estimates are presented in Table 7, and the plots of the correlations in Figure 5.

We note that for the pairs Brent-GRNFUEL and Brent-GRNBIO the coefficient a_1 was insignificantly different from 0. The latter is evident for Brent-GRNBIO, where the correlation was almost static in time (black line in Figure 5). GRNBIO index tracks companies that produce energy through fuel cells. Fuel cell electric vehicles are considered

Table 3

Estimates of GJR-GARCH model with skewed Student distribution for Brent oil

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
μ	0.001	0.001	0.975	0.330
ω	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.000	3.382	0.001
α	0.060	0.026	2.312	0.021
β	0.856	0.026	32.781	< 0.001
γ	0.110	0.040	2.718	0.007
κ	0.863	0.033	25.933	< 0.001
ν	3.708	0.447	8.294	< 0.001

Note: ν denotes the number of degrees of freedom in the skewed Student distribution, while κ is the parameter of the asymmetry of the distribution. The best model was fit to the data based on its ability to explain all linear and non-linear dependencies in the time series. All the parameters were stable according to the Nyblom stability test. The model passed Pearson's goodness of fit test. According to the sign-bias test, there was no positive nor negative bias in the residuals, yet - we did not explain the total asymmetry (the joint effect was still present).

Table 4

Estimates of GARCH(1,1) with Student distribution for GRNFUEL

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
μ	$-2.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.001	-0.029	0.977
ω	$0.9 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.000	1.531	0.126
α	0.073	0.016	4.444	< 0.001
β	0.926	0.015	60.424	< 0.001
ν	5.448	0.848	6.426	< 0.001

Note: ν denotes the number of degrees of freedom in the skewed Student distribution. The best model was fit to the data based on its ability to explain all linear and non-linear dependencies in the time series. All the parameters apart from ν were stable according to the Nyblom stability test. The model passed Pearson's goodness of fit test. According to the sign-bias test, there was no positive nor negative bias in the residuals.

Table 5

Estimates of GARCH(1,1) model with skewed Student error distribution for GRNBIO

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
μ	0.000	0.001	0.719	0.472
α	0.083	0.007	12.122	< 0.001
β	0.897	0.008	108.110	< 0.001
κ	0.943	0.040	23.726	< 0.001
ν	7.233	1.299	5.568	< 0.001
ω	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	-	-

Note: ν denotes the number of degrees of freedom in the skewed Student distribution, while κ is the distribution's asymmetry parameter. The best model was fit to the data based on its ability to explain all linear and non-linear dependencies in the time series. All the parameters were stable according to the Nyblom stability test. The model passed Pearson's goodness of fit test.

According to the sign-bias test, there was no positive nor negative bias in the residuals. In the estimation, we applied the variance-targeting option. Variance targeting replaces the intercept ω in the variance equation by one minus the persistence multiplied by the unconditional variance [22].

an alternative to battery electric vehicles, now the preferred technology for urban freight transport. Thus, it is to a lesser degree related to the issue of replacing fossil fuels with green fuels but rather one green technology with another [57].

Another index for which the DCC parameter a_1 was insignificantly different from 0 was GRNFUEL. GRNFUEL tracks companies that manufacture fuels from plant-based materials. The correlation series were positive throughout the whole period of study.

The DCC parameters of the Brent correlation with the remaining index (GRNTRN) were significant. The correlation of GRNTRN was negative in some subperiods, which means that Brent and the index changed in opposite directions. The subperiods included the beginning of April and the beginning of October 2018, mid-September 2019,

Table 6
Estimates of GARCH model with Student distribution for GRNTRN

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
μ	0.001	0.000	2.255	0.024
α	0.090	0.001	137.513	< 0.001
β	0.906	0.000	3146.907	< 0.001
ν	6.091	0.752	8.101	< 0.001
ω	$2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	—	—	—

Note: ν denotes the number of degrees of freedom in the Student distribution. The best model was fit to the data based on its ability to explain all linear and non-linear dependencies in the time series. All the parameters were stable according to the Nyblom stability test. The model passed Pearson's goodness of fit test. According to the sign-bias test, there was no positive nor negative bias in the residuals. In the estimation, we applied the variance-targeting option. Variance targeting replaces the intercept ω in the variance equation by one minus the persistence multiplied by the unconditional variance [22].

Figure 4: Volatility of Brent and GRNBIO (a), GRNFUEL (b), GRNTRN (c) from January 2018 to September 2022

Note Volatilities of green indices are printed in solid green line, while volatility of Brent - black dotted line.

January and February 2020, November 2021, February-March 2022 and August 2022. GRNTRN tracks companies that focus on pollution reduction and are associated with cars, trains, and other means of transport.

Next, we transform the daily correlation series into monthly ones, taking as an estimate the average value of the correlation. Eventually, we estimate linear regression models where the regressors are the fundamental factors driving oil price dynamics, the speculation-related factors and S&P 500 returns (as a proxy for the overall condition in financial markets).

As an opening step, we used the Bayesian model averaging technique to select the best set of regressors for the final model. In Table 8, we present the posterior probabilities for each variable to be included in the final model, together with the expected values and standard deviations. We bolded the variables for which the posterior probabilities exceeded 0.5. These variables belong to the fundamentals driving oil prices (world industrial production, global economic conditions, demand shock driven by economic activity and oil consumption demand shock). We note that the algorithm did not select the factors related to speculation as the influential ones. Comparing the posterior probabilities of the two speculation-related factors across the models for three indices, we note the highest one (of 21.7%) for L.SPC in the model for correlation between Brent and GRNFUEL, with a negative expected value.

In Table 9, we present the estimates of the final linear model, and in Table 10, the multicollinearity diagnostics. We infer from Tables 8–9 that fundamental factors play a predominant role in shaping the correlation between Brent and indices related to alternative transport. Positive oil supply shocks contribute to the decrease in correlation, while the negative - to its increase. Two demand shocks can impact the correlations: consumption demand and shocks related to economic activity.

Oil consumption demand shock was significant in the GRNBIO and GRNTRN regression models. The relationship was negative, meaning that the positive oil consumption demand shocks lowered the correlation. Thus, if the demand for oil consumption grows, the investors may remove their capital from the alternative fuel market and green transport sector and locate them in the oil one.

Figure 5: Dynamic conditional correlations between Brent and each green index

Demand shocks related to economic activity drove the correlation between Brent and GRNFUEL, and Brent-GRNBIO. They were positively related to correlation. According to [7], for oil demand shocks driven by global economic activity, all economies experience a temporary increase in real GDP following an oil price increase. Thus, the increase in correlation as a consequence of that kind of shock may signal the overall increase in economic conditions. In this case, the growth in oil prices would be accompanied by the growth in green indices.

The changes in the index of global economic condition [4] were negatively related to the correlation between Brent - GRNBIO and Brent - GRNTRN. From the theoretical point of view, the growing global economy increases the total demand in the global commodity market, which results in a large increase in crude oil price [41]. When the GECON index increases, investors anticipate improving economic conditions, which results in high oil prices, increasing costs of biofuel production (GRNBIO) and green transport (GRNTRN). Expecting oil prices to go up, they are more likely to invest in oil than in biofuels to be the beneficiaries of the profits. Thus, rising oil prices will be followed by falling prices of GRNTRN and GRNBIO.

This conclusion is also consistent with the results obtained for the variable describing changes in oil price expectations (D.EXP) in the case of the GRNFUEL index. Expectations regarding oil prices were negatively related to the correlation between Brent and GRNFUEL. Thus, when investors expect an increase in oil prices, they may remove their wealth from the fuel cell sector.

6. Discussion and conclusions

The research aimed to determine the relationships between the returns of oil and alternative fuels during stress episodes. We aimed to verify whether the increases in oil prices can suppress the evolution of the green transportation market. The effect of the shift in oil prices can be twofold. From the demand side, the increase in oil prices translates

Table 7

Estimates of the parameters of dynamic conditional correlation between Brent and green indices

Coefficient	Estimate	std.error	t-stat	p.value
GRNFUEL				
<i>a</i>	0.014	0.017	0.788	0.431
<i>b</i>	0.815	0.094	8.658	0.000
<i>k</i>	4.796	0.337	14.245	0.000
GRNBIO				
<i>a</i>	0.000	0.000	0.010	0.992
<i>b</i>	0.905	0.143	6.309	0.000
<i>k</i>	5.493	0.505	10.881	0.000
GRNTRN				
<i>a</i>	0.075	0.028	2.696	0.007
<i>b</i>	0.636	0.103	6.151	0.000
<i>k</i>	4.799	0.367	13.090	0.000

Note: *k* denotes the number of degrees of freedom in Student's distribution

Table 8

Bayesian model averaging - selection of explanatory variables

Index	measure	Intercept	D.WIP	COM	D.GECON	S.SH	EASH	OCDSH	OIDSH	D.GEPU	D.EXP	L.SPC	D.SPC	D.SPX
GRNFUEL	$p \neq 0$	100	22.4	5.2	27.3	32.3	64	29.7	5.4	34.9	44.6	21.7	6.4	6.4
	EV	0.233	0.049	0.000	-0.001	-0.001	0.003	0.000	0.000	0.007	-0.022	-0.002	-0.006	-0.001
	SD	0.046	0.175	0.001	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.000	0.000	0.012	0.030	0.004	0.041	0.012
GRNBIO	$p \neq 0$	100	19.8	3	87.7	9.9	97.3	83.3	13.5	3.5	19.7	4.7	14.4	8.3
	EV	2.93E-01	-3.51E-06	-1.35E-09	-2.37E-07	-5.73E-09	2.47E-07	-4.63E-08	1.40E-08	-1.02E-08	-3.66E-07	5.44E-09	-9.39E-07	1.31E-07
	SD	5.55E-07	9.85E-06	2.76E-08	1.29E-07	2.45E-08	1.14E-07	2.57E-08	4.65E-08	9.92E-08	8.71E-07	4.43E-08	2.96E-06	6.06E-07
GRNTRN	$p \neq 0$	100	56.1	4.7	50.2	17.3	44	94.9	11.5	36.8	12.6	4.5	12.2	5.9
	EV	0.184	0.717	0.000	-0.008	-0.001	0.005	-0.004	0.001	0.022	0.002	0.000	-0.056	0.004
	SD	0.035	0.761	0.003	0.010	0.002	0.007	0.002	0.003	0.036	0.041	0.003	0.199	0.032

Note: $p \neq 0$ denotes the posterior probability that the variable is non-zero, EV-posterior expected value and SD-posterior standard deviation

into the growth of traditional travelling costs, and hence, consumers may start looking for alternative transport modes or fuels. However, from the investors' point of view, rising oil prices create an opportunity to obtain abnormal returns from the investment in crude. Thus, it may happen that the investors would direct their attention to the black energy investment and withdraw their funds from the green energy sector.

This article analyzes Brent oil prices with three green indices: GRNBIO, GRNFUEL, and GRNTRN. GRNBIO tracks companies that manufacture fuels from plant-based materials that replace petroleum-based fuels for transportation. GRNFUEL represents companies that produce energy through fuel cells. Eventually, GRNTRN tracks companies concentrated on efficiency gains and pollution reduction associated with automobiles, trains, and other modes of transportation. We focused on the period from 01.01.2018 to 31.12.2022.

We estimated volatility models for Brent and each index, derived dynamic correlation for each pair, and analysed the dynamics of the correlations concerning the changes in fundamentals and speculative factors related to oil price volatility. The correlations appeared to be positive for each index - only the correlation between Brent and GRNTRN occasionally reached negative values.

We identified the factors that contributed to the declines in correlations and, as such, may cause them to be negative in the future. Supply shock and oil consumption demand shock could cause the weakening of the relationships between oil and alternative fuels. Besides, expectations regarding the development of oil prices and changes in global economic conditions were crucial for lowering the correlation between Brent and green indices.

Oil demand shock related to economic activity and changes in world industrial production were positively related to the correlations, which signifies that the decline in economic conditions during oil price falls contributes to the decrease in the interest in alternative fuels as well (see also [47] and [51]). That indicates the need for governmental support for the green market during such periods.

Table 9

Influence of fundamental and financial factors on correlation between Brent and green indices - linear regression estimates

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
Brent-GRNFUEL R2=0.18				
(Intercept)	0.213	0.002	114.615	0.000
S.SH	-0.003	0.001	-2.222	0.030
EASH	0.004	0.001	3.106	0.003
D.EXP	-0.066	0.019	-3.577	0.001
Brent-GRNBIO R2=0.35				
(Intercept)	0.293	0.000	4300372.168	0.000
D.GECON	$-2.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.000	-2.997	0.004
EASH	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.000	3.621	0.001
OCDSH	$-5.3 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.000	-3.627	0.001
BRENT-GRNTRN R2=0.32				
(Intercept)	0.182	0.005	34.767	0.000
D.WIP	1.553	0.414	3.752	0.000
D.GECON	-0.017	0.007	-2.338	0.023
OCDSH	-0.004	0.001	-3.227	0.002

Note: COMM denotes commodities price index, D.GECON - the change of global economic conditions, S.SH - the oil supply shock, OCDSH - oil consumption demand shock, OIDSH - oil inventory demand shock, D.GEPU - the change of global policy uncertainty index, EASH - oil demand shock resulting from economic activity, D.EXP- change in expectations regarding oil prices, D.SPC - change in modified Working index [59], L.SPC - logarithm of the net position of money managers in oil market

Table 10

Multicollinearity diagnostic

Variables	Tolerance	VIF
GRNFUEL		
S.SH	0.494	2.022
EASH	0.726	1.377
D.EXP	0.413	2.420
GRNBIO		
D.GECON	0.607	1.649
EASH	0.643	1.555
OCDSH	0.901	1.109
GRNTRN		
D.WIP	0.579	1.728
D.GECON	0.541	1.848
OCDSH	0.902	1.109

Note: VIF denotes variance inflation factor

Moreover, when the investors anticipate the increase in overall economic conditions, they may anticipate a boost in the overall interest in alternative transport very soon as a consequence of the increases in oil prices (positive relationship with EASH), but probably also due to the regulations that favour alternative transport modes.

Eventually, we found that the relationship between crude oil and green indices does not depend on the activities of speculators in the oil market. This result partially confirms the findings of researchers who document that the volatility of oil [44, 34] or renewables [19] depends mostly on fundamental factors and speculation forces are less important. We document their limited impact on the correlation between Brent and the analysed indices.

Regarding the question formulated in the title, we can summarise the results, as follows. The impact of rising oil prices can have two different outcomes for the alternative transportation market, depending on the reason behind that change. It can amplify the interest in indices related to alternative transport if oil prices growth is a result of oil demand shock driven by economic activity. However, if the rise in prices follows positive oil consumption demand shocks or market participants' expectations of future oil price increase, it can cause a capital outflow from the alternative transportation market. Thus, policymakers should be aware not only of the direction of oil price changes, but also on their origin.

The research has some limitations. First, we analyse the correlation between Brent and indices. In the case of crude oil, several primary benchmarks can be analysed similarly, i.e. WTI, Dubai and Brent. We chose Brent because Brent Crude is often considered the world benchmark for oil and reflects global oil market fundamentals. However, WTI attracts a higher proportion of non-commercial investors than Brent [58]; hence, it would be interesting to determine whether a speculation factor would be more influential on the correlations between oil and green transportation indices. Moreover, green indices encompass a heterogeneous mix of assets, making it difficult to justify their direct comparison and explain the relationships. Secondly, we analysed only a limited set of possible regressors that could impact the correlation. Lastly, the dynamic correlation is only one way of measuring the interrelationships between assets. In further work, we focus on the impact of the fundamentals and speculation on tail relationships between Brent and green indices.

List of abbreviations:

- ARMA-GARCH - autoregressive moving-average model with generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity;
- COMM - real commodity price (index);
- D.SPC - changes of the speculative activity of non-commercial traders in the crude oil market (index);
- EASH - oil demand shock driven by global economic activity;
- ETF - exchange-traded fund;
- EXP - Brent spot prices expectations formulated by US Energy Information Association (index);
- GECON - global economic condition (index);
- GEPU - global economic uncertainty (index);
- GRNBIO - NASDAQ OMX Bio/Clean Fuels Index;
- GRNFUEL - NASDAQ OMX Fuel Cell Index;
- GRNTRN - NASDAQ OMX Transportation Index;
- IEA - International Energy Agency;
- L.SPC - logarithm of the net position of Money Managers for Brent contract;
- NASDAQ - National Association of Securities Dealers Automated Quotations (an American stock market that handles electronic securities trading around the world),
- OCDSH - oil consumption demand shock;
- OISH - oil inventory demand (shock);
- S&P - Standard and Poor's Index;
- S.SH - oil supply shock;
- VAR - vector autoregressive model;
- VaR - Value at Risk.
- WIP - world industrial production (index)

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Agata Kliber: Conceptualization, Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Software, Validation, Formal analysis. **Blanka Let:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Writing - Original draft preparation, Software, Validation, Formal analysis. **Pavel Rezac:** Investigation, Writing - Original draft preparation.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the support of the National Science Centre (NCN) in Poland under grant no. 2022/45/B/HS4/00864 and Czech Ministry of Transport within the programme of long-term conceptual development of research institutions, grant no 55/2020-710-VV/1. We would like to thank the participants of SENAMEK seminar (27.09.2023, Warsaw School of Economics) for discussion and comments on the early version of this paper.

References

- [1] Alexopoulos, T.A., 2018. To trust or not to trust? A comparative study of conventional and clean energy exchange-traded funds. *Energy Economics* 72, 97–107. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S014098831830094X>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2018.03.013>.
- [2] Angelini, E., Birindelli, G., Chiappini, H., Foglia, M., 2022. Clean energy indices and brown assets: an analysis of tail risk spillovers through the VAR for VaR model. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment* 0, 1–28. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/20430795.2022.2105788>, doi:10.1080/20430795.2022.2105788, arXiv:<https://doi.org/10.1080/20430795.2022.2105788>.
- [3] Baker, S.R., Bloom, N., Davis, S.J., 2016. Measuring economic policy uncertainty. *The quarterly journal of economics* 131, 1593–1636.
- [4] Baumeister, C., Guérin, P., 2021. A comparison of monthly global indicators for forecasting growth. *International Journal of Forecasting* 37, 1276–1295.
- [5] Baumeister, C., Hamilton, J.D., 2019. Structural interpretation of vector autoregressions with incomplete identification: Revisiting the role of oil supply and demand shocks. *American Economic Review* 109, 1873–1910.
- [6] Baumeister, C., Korobilis, D., Lee, T.K., 2022. Energy markets and global economic conditions. *Review of Economics and Statistics* 104, 828–844.
- [7] Baumeister, C., Peersman, G., Van Robays, I., et al., 2010. The economic consequences of oil shocks: differences across countries and time. Inflation in an era of relative price shocks. *Reserve Bank of Australia*, 91–128.
- [8] Baur, D.G., Todorova, N., 2018. Automobile manufacturers, electric vehicles and the price of oil. *Energy Economics* 74, 252–262. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S014098831830207X>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2018.05.034>.
- [9] Björklund, M., 2011. Influence from the business environment on environmental purchasing—drivers and hinders of purchasing green transportation services. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management* 17, 11–22.
- [10] Bollerslev, T., 1986. Generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity. *Journal of Econometrics* 31, 307–327.
- [11] Büyükaşahin, B., Harris, J.H., 2011. Do speculators drive crude oil futures prices? *The Energy Journal* 32, 167–202. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41323326>.
- [12] Candelon, B., Tokpavi, S., 2016. A nonparametric test for granger causality in distribution with application to financial contagion. *Journal of Business Economic Statistics* 34, 240–253. URL: <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:taf:jnlbes:v:34:y:2016:i:2:p:240-253>.
- [13] Chambers, M., Bailey, R., 1996. A theory of commodity price fluctuations. *Journal of Political Economy* 104, 924–57. URL: <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:ucp:jpolec:v:104:y:1996:i:5:p:924-57>.
- [14] Chang, C.L., McAleer, M., Wang, Y.A., 2020. Herding behaviour in energy stock markets during the global financial crisis, sars, and ongoing COVID-19*. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 134, 110349. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032120306377>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110349>.
- [15] Chang, T.H., Su, H.M., 2010. The substitutive effect of biofuels on fossil fuels in the lower and higher crude oil price periods. *Energy* 35, 2807–2813. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544210001246>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2010.03.006>.
- [16] Cortez, M.C., Andrade, N., Silva, F., 2022. The environmental and financial performance of green energy investments: European evidence. *Ecological Economics* 197, 107427. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921800922000891>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107427>.
- [17] Dawar, I., Dutta, A., Bouri, E., Saeed, T., 2021. Crude oil prices and clean energy stock indices: Lagged and asymmetric effects with quantile regression. *Renewable Energy* 163, 288–299. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148120314051>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.08.162>.
- [18] Dedi, V., Mandilaras, A., 2022. Trader positions and the price of oil in the futures market. *International Review of Economics Finance* 82, 448–460. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1059056022001782>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2022.06.018>.
- [19] Dutta, A., Dutta, P., 2022. Geopolitical risk and renewable energy asset prices: Implications for sustainable development. *Renewable Energy* 196, 518–525. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148122010254>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.07.029>.
- [20] Dvir, E., Rogoff, K., 2014. Demand effects and speculation in oil markets: Theory and evidence. *Journal of International Money and Finance* 42, 113–128. URL: <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:eee:jimfin:v:42:y:2014:i:c:p:113-128>.
- [21] Engle, R., 2002. Dynamic conditional correlation: A simple class of multivariate generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity models. *Journal of Business Economic Statistics* 20, 339–350. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1392121>.
- [22] Engle, R., Mezrich, J., 1996. GARCH for groups: A round-up of recent developments in GARCH techniques for estimating correlation. *RISK-LONDON-RISK MAGAZINE LIMITED-* 9, 36–40.
- [23] Fattouh, B., Kilian, L., Mahadeva, L., 2013. The role of speculation in oil markets: What have we learned so far? *The Energy Journal* 34.

- [24] Filis, G., Degiannakis, S., Floros, C., 2011. Dynamic correlation between stock market and oil prices: The case of oil-importing and oil-exporting countries. *International Review of Financial Analysis* 20, 152–164. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2011.02.014>, doi:10.1016/j.irfa.2011.02.014.
- [25] Fiszeder, P., Faldziński, M., Molnár, P., 2023. Attention to oil prices and its impact on the oil, gold and stock markets and their covariance. *Energy Economics* 120, 106643.
- [26] Foglia, M., Angelini, E., Huynh, T.L.D., 2022. Tail risk connectedness in clean energy and oil financial market. *Annals of Operations Research* URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10479-022-04745-w>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-022-04745-w>.
- [27] Galanos, A., 2019. rmgarch: Multivariate GARCH models. R package version 1.3-6.
- [28] Garcia-Amate, A., Ramírez-Orellana, A., Ramirez, A.A.R., 2021. Is it attractive to invest in alternative energy? Evidence from a five-factor fama-french model for regional DJSI and renewable stock indexes. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal* 13, 273–296. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1108/sampj-09-2020-0317>, doi:10.1108/sampj-09-2020-0317.
- [29] Geng, J.B., Liu, C., Ji, Q., Zhang, D., 2021. Do oil price changes really matter for clean energy returns? *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 150, 111429. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032121007127>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111429>.
- [30] Ghalanos, A., 2014. rugarch: Univariate GARCH models. R package version 1.4-0.
- [31] Glosten, L.R., Jagannathan, R., Runkle, D.E., 1993. On the relation between the expected value and the volatility of the nominal excess return on stocks. *The Journal of Finance* 48, 1779–1801. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1993.tb05128.x>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1993.tb05128.x>, arXiv:<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1993.tb05128.x>.
- [32] Hanif, W., Teplova, T., Rodina, V., Alomari, M., Mensi, W., 2023. Volatility spillovers and frequency dependence between oil price shocks and green stock markets. *Resources Policy* 85, 103860. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301420723005718>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2023.103860>.
- [33] IEA, 2020. *Energy Technology Perspectives 2020*. IEA, Paris.
- [34] Kaufmann, R.K., Connelly, C., 2020. Non-market forces significantly affect oil prices. *Nature Energy* 5, 129–130. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-020-0563-3>, doi:10.1038/s41560-020-0563-3.
- [35] Kilian, L., 2008. The economic effects of energy price shocks. *Journal of Economic Literature* 46, 871–909. doi:10.1257/jel.46.4.871.
- [36] Kilian, L., Murphy, D.P., 2014. The role of inventories and speculative trading in the global market for crude oil. *Journal of Applied Econometrics* 29, 454–478. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/jae.2322>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.2322>, arXiv:<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/jae.2322>.
- [37] Kliber, A., Łęt, B., 2022. Degree of connectedness and the transfer of news across the oil market and the european stocks. *Energy* 239, 122171.
- [38] Kuang, W., 2021. Which clean energy sectors are attractive? A portfolio diversification perspective. *Energy Economics* 104, 105644. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140988321005028>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105644>.
- [39] Lee, C.T., Hashim, H., Ho, C.S., Fan, Y.V., Klemeš, J.J., 2017. Sustaining the low-carbon emission development in Asia and beyond: Sustainable energy, water, transportation and low-carbon emission technology. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 146, 1–13. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652616320066>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.11.144>. bridging the Gaps for Accelerating Low Carbon Actions in Asia.
- [40] Liu, Z., Zhang, H., Ding, Z., Lv, T., Wang, X., Wang, D., 2022. When are the effects of economic policy uncertainty on oil-stock correlations larger? evidence from a regime-switching analysis. *Economic Modelling* 114, 105941. doi:10.1016/j.econmod.2022.105941.
- [41] Lv, W., Wu, Q., 2022. Global economic conditions index and oil price predictability. *Finance Research Letters* 48, 102919. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1544612322001891>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2022.102919>.
- [42] Martí-Ballester, C.P., 2019. Do european renewable energy mutual funds foster the transition to a low-carbon economy? *Renewable Energy* 143, 1299–1309. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148119307682>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.05.095>.
- [43] Miralles-Quirós, J.L., Miralles-Quirós, M.M., 2019. Are alternative energies a real alternative for investors? *Energy Economics* 78, 535–545. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140988318304900>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2018.12.008>.
- [44] Mohsin, M., Jamaani, F., 2023. Green finance and the socio-politico-economic factors' impact on the future oil prices: Evidence from machine learning. *Resources Policy* 85, 103780. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301420723004919>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2023.103780>.
- [45] Oberling, D.F., Obermaier, M., Szklo, A., La Rovere, E.L., 2012. Investments of oil majors in liquid biofuels: The role of diversification, integration and technological lock-ins. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 46, 270–281. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0961953412003315>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2012.08.017>. international Conference on Lignocellulosic ethanol.
- [46] Pham, L., 2019. Do all clean energy stocks respond homogeneously to oil price? *Energy Economics* 81, 355–379. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140988319301240>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2019.04.010>.
- [47] Reboredo, J.C., 2015. Is there dependence and systemic risk between oil and renewable energy stock prices? *Energy Economics* 48, 32–45. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140988314003259>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2014.12.009>.
- [48] Reboredo, J.C., Quintela, M., Otero, L.A., 2017. Do investors pay a premium for going green? Evidence from alternative energy mutual funds. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 73, 512–520. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032117301600>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.01.158>.

- [49] Rezec, M., Scholtens, B., 2017. Financing energy transformation: The role of renewable energy equity indices. *International Journal of Green Energy* 14, 368–378. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15435075.2016.1261704>, doi:10.1080/15435075.2016.1261704, arXiv:<https://doi.org/10.1080/15435075.2016.1261704>.
- [50] Ritchie, H., 2020. Cars, planes, trains: where do CO2 emissions from transport come from? *OurWorldInData.com* URL: <https://ourworldindata.org/co2-emissions-from-transport>. accessed: 04.11.2022.
- [51] Shah, I.H., Hiles, C., Morley, B., 2018. How do oil prices, macroeconomic factors and policies affect the market for renewable energy? *Applied Energy* 215, 87–97. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261918300990>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.01.084>.
- [52] Shah, K.J., Pan, S.Y., Lee, I., Kim, H., You, Z., Zheng, J.M., Chiang, P.C., 2021. Green transportation for sustainability: Review of current barriers, strategies, and innovative technologies. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 326, 129392. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652621035769>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129392>.
- [53] Si Mohammed, K., Mellit, A., 2023. The relationship between oil prices and the indices of renewable energy and technology companies based on qqr and gcq techniques. *Renewable Energy* 209, 97–105. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148123004263>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.03.123>.
- [54] Tan, X., Geng, Y., Vivian, A., Wang, X., 2021. Measuring risk spillovers between oil and clean energy stocks: Evidence from a systematic framework. *Resources Policy* 74, 102406. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301420721004153>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2021.102406>.
- [55] Tsao, Y.C., Vu, T.L., Lu, J.C., 2021. Pricing, capacity and financing policies for investment of renewable energy generations. *Applied Energy* 303, 117664. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261921010278>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117664>.
- [56] Vansteenkiste, I., 2011. What is driving oil futures prices? fundamentals versus speculation. *ECB Working Paper Series* 1371, 4–27. URL: <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/research/authors/profiles/isabel-vansteenkiste.en.html>.
- [57] Winkler, J.K., Grahle, A., Syré, A.M., Martins-Turner, K., Göhlich, D., 2022. Fuel cell drive for urban freight transport in comparison to diesel and battery electric drives: a case study of the food retailing industry in Berlin. *European Transport Research Review* 14. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-022-00525-6>, doi:10.1186/s12544-022-00525-6.
- [58] Wittner, M., 2020. What are the differences between ICE Brent and NYMEX WTI Futures? Technical Report. Intercontinental Exchange, Inc. URL: https://www.fia.org/sites/default/files/2020-06/ICE_Brent%20vs%20WTI%20Whitepaper%20-%20PDF%20version.pdf.
- [59] Working, H., 1960. Speculation on Hedging Markets. *Food Research Institute Studies* 1, 1–36. URL: <https://ideas.repec.org/a/ags/frisst/136578.html>, doi:10.22004/ag.econ.136578.
- [60] Yahya, M., Dutta, A., Bouri, E., Wadström, C., Uddin, G.S., 2022. Dependence structure between the international crude oil market and the european markets of biodiesel and rapeseed oil. *Renewable Energy* 197, 594–605. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148122011168>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.07.112>.
- [61] Zhou, W., Chen, Y., Chen, J., 2022. Risk spread in multiple energy markets: Extreme volatility spillover network analysis before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Energy* 256, 124580. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544222014839>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.124580>.